

Research

Geotechnical Properties of Lateritic Soil for Sub Base And Base Materials for Road Construction in Nyaruguru District, Rwanda

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Abstract: Lateritic soils have wider applications in Rwandan construction industry, especially in road-construction projects where they are used as filling materials in flexible pavement foundations. This study is aimed to analyze the quality and suitability of the lateritic soils for Sub base and base materials for road construction in Nyaruguru District, Rwanda.

This is research utilized an experimental study design approach to implement this study. Four sites were chosen due to their closeness to construction sites and ease of sample availability throughout Nyaruguru district from which disturbed and undisturbed lateritic soil samples at a depth of 2 m were collected. The collected samples were analyzed with a series of standardized laboratory tests for soil to determine their properties and usage in road construction.

The study findings show that particle size distribution of lateritic soils found throughout all samples have high quantity of coarse gravelly soil, the average is 46.81% apart from sample SL3 which had 26.04%, by using USC classification shown that all sites are gravelly silt except SL1 which is CL (sand lean clay with gravel). Natural moisture content range between 11.38 to 19% and mean value was observed at 15.31%. Maximum dry unit weight (MDD) and optimum moisture content (OMC) were found to be 2 KN/m³ and 2.43 % respectively. The specific gravity ranges between 2.66 and 2.93 with an average of 2.77. Liquid limits range between 23.2 to 35.5%, plastic limits 15 to 27.1% and plasticity index 6 to 10%. Average cohesion and angle of internal friction are 31.5 KN and 55.7° respectively. The CBR ranges from 14.17 to 32.9%.

The results show that lateritic soils from Nyaruguru district of Rwanda in area SL1, SL2, SL3 and SL4 are suitable for sub-grade whereas SL1 and SL2 are also suitable for sub-base material since their geotechnical properties are fairly within the regulatory standards.

Keywords: Lateritic soil, Geotechnical engineering properties, Sub base & Base Coarse, Road construction materials, geotechnical engineering properties.

1. Introduction

Laterite (Derived from the Latin word later meaning brick) is a surface formation in hot and wet tropical areas which is enriched in iron and aluminum and develops by intensive and long lasting weathering of the underlying parent rock. Laterites are soils formed from disintegration of rocks through the process of weathering and laterization (second weathering). Parent rock are broken down into soil through the process of physical and chemical weathering which takes place simultaneously (Addson, June 2008).

Laterites are widely distributed throughout the world in the regions with high rainfall, but especially in the inter-tropical regions of Africa, Australia, India, South-East Asia and South America, where they generally occur just below the surface of grasslands or forest clearings. Their extension indicates that conditions were favorable for their formation at some point in time in the history of the world, but not necessarily simultaneously in all regions (Patrick N. Lemounga, 2011).

Moreover, in the tropical part of the world, lateritic soil is used as a road making material and it forms the sub-grade of most tropical roads, sub-base and base course for low cost roads which tend to carry low to medium traffic. Furthermore, road network plays a vital role in socio-economic development of many nations. However, there is lack of in-depth understanding of the geotechnical properties of soils which is a precondition for its use in civil engineering construction works (Ademila, August 2017).

In Rwanda lateritic soils have wider applications in construction industry, especially in road-construction projects where they are used as filling materials in flexible pavement foundations. Their usage as sub-base and base construction materials is mainly because they are easy to manipulate on the road surface and have natural stable grading with a suitable proportion to act as binders (Layade Gideon Oluyinka 1*, January 2018). However, failure of lateritic roads in developing countries including Rwanda has stressed the need for detailed geotechnical evaluation of lateritic soil prior its use in road construction in order to choose appropriate soil materials for the pavement structure (Ademila, August 2017). For a material to be used as either a base or sub-base course depends on its strength in transmitting the axle-load to the sub-soil and or sub-grade (the mechanical interlock). The characteristics and durability of any constructional material is a function of its efficiency in response to the load applied on it (Amadi A.N.*, January 03, 2015). The performance of lateritic soils as foundations for structure is varied and

appears to depend on the nature of the soil, the degree of the weathering, topography, the drainage condition and more importantly on the type of foundation, and the amount of loads imposed (Layade Gideon Oluyinka 1*, 2018).

Rwanda's Vision 2020 and its medium term development strategy Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy (EDPRS II) seeks to encourage a market oriented production and to encourage diversification to nontraditional crops of high potential for exports, as well as food security and import substitution. This is to be accomplished by investing in rural infrastructure and increasing agricultural productivity. This strategy identifies improving District roads as a means for rural development. Furthermore, agricultural initiatives stress the need to develop agricultural marketing roads to reduce both postharvest loss and the price of delivering agricultural inputs in the project areas (Intercontinental Consultants and Technocrats Pvt, February, 2017). According to Jour et al in their study, the gravelly lateritic soils are a raw material in the civil engineering sector for implementation of the road infrastructures in order to promote national exchanges (TY-JOUR, 2017).

Moreover, Nyaruguru District is the one of districts that was chosen to have the feeder road development project (Intercontinental Consultants and Technocrats Pvt, February, 2017). The presence of lateritic soils which can be used as the raw material in road construction in the district is an asset; however there is paucity of data regarding geotechnical properties of these lateritic soils to determine its usage. Therefore, the aim of this study was to analyze the geotechnical properties of lateritic soils present in Nyaruguru district to determine their specific usage for road construction projects.

2. Materials and methods

Lateritic soil samples were collected from Nyaruguru District in Rwanda specifically from SL1, SL2, SL3 and SL4. Furthermore, SL1 is located near SHILI, SL2 at Munini hospital, SL3 near Kivu at Remera, and SL4 at Nshili -Remera road. The sites were chosen due to their closeness to construction sites and ease of sample availability, lending to the ease of soil sample collection, some of the chosen sites are used in different projects in Nyaruguru district such NSHILI-REMERERA Road by engineering brigade and Munini hospital construction terrain preparation by Hygebat Ltd (NYARUGURU, 2018).

Sampling was made by collecting disturbed undisturbed samples from the four sites. Moreover, undisturbed samples were excavated at the depth of 2m in four open pits by using covered plastic tube to avoid losing nature condition to obtain required condition of some tests like shear, consolidation and also nature moisture content as it stated by British standard BS 1377:1990 part 7: Clause 4 (Procedure 8), BS 1377:1990 part 5: Clause 3 (BSI, 1990).

An experimental study design was used to implement this study to determine geotechnical properties of the lateritic soils and its usefulness in road construction. Experimental method deals with the future. That means it tries to predict what will happen in the future by studying the relationship between the variables under study (Creswell, 2002). An experimental design is regarded as the most accurate form of experimental research, in that it tries to prove or disprove a hypothesis mathematically, with statistical analysis. Furthermore, it is standard and commonly used in physical sciences, such as physics, chemistry and geology (Syed Muhammad Sajjad Kabir, 2016). In this study a series of analyses were performed in soil mechanics laboratory of Integrated Polytechnic Regional Center-Huye. Furthermore the analyses included Specific gravity, Particle size Distribution, Moisture content, Maximum dry unit weight, optimum moisture content, Plastic limit, Liquid limit, Shear strength, California Bearing Ratio, and consolidation test. The results were interpreted following national and international standards.

3. Results

3.1 Summary of Results

The summary of the result conducted in test done on lateritic soils from NYARUGURU District SL1, SL2, SL3, SL4 are summarized in table 1.

Tests	SL1 Results	SL2 Results	SL3 Results	SL4 Results
Moisture Content (%)	13.49	19	11.38	17.395
Proctor test				
γ_{dmax} (Mg/m ³)	1.981	1.985	2.02	2.019
OMC (%)	8.72	10.5	9.26	9.25
Particle Size Analysis (%)				
Gravel	53.45	62.58	26.04	45.18
Sand	30.63	25.32	50.68	35.99
Fines	15.92	12.10	23.29	18.83
Liquid Limit (%)	33.5	28.1	33.2	23.3
Plastic Limit (%)	24.4	18.2	27.1	15
Plasticity Index (PI) (%)	9	10	6	8
Specific Gravity	2.73	2.76	2.66	2.93
CBR Test (%)	32.90	23.78	15.64	14.17
Direct Shear Test C(KPa)	39.1	23.1	17.1	46.7
ϕ (Degree)	58.1	55.9	51.7	57.2

Table 1: Summary of Test Results

3.2 Specific gravity

The specific gravity (GS) of air dried samples collected were determined as described in BS 1377- 2:1990 (BSI, 1990) and ASTM-D854,/.i. the specific gravity is used in engineering to determine the air void ratio, particle size distribution in hydrometer analysis and degree of

saturation (ASTM International, 2018). The table 2 summarizes specific gravity results of studied lateritic soils.

Sites	Natural Moisture (%)	Sample Condition	Specific gravity
SL1	13.49	Air dried	2.73
SL2	19	Air dried	2.76
SL3	11.38	Air dried	2.66
SL4	17.39	Air dried	2.93
Average			2.77

Table 2: Specific Gravity Results

3.3 Sieve analysis

Wet sieves analysis was performed in four samples and all were sampled in wet condition exposed in air dry in period of four days on flat terrain to remove the water content to obtain initial weight to be used during testing then after sample transfer to sieve of 0.075 mm to get fine material by using USC in classification for all samples retained on 0.075 is greater than 50% is coarse soil as it described in BS 1377- 2:1990 (BSI, 1990). All sample graphs are described in table 3.

Site	Gravelly % 74 to 4.75 mm	Sand % 4.75 to 0.075mm	Fines % >0.075mm	classification
SL1	53.45	30.63	15.92	CL(sand lean clay with gravel)
SL2	62.58	25.32	12.10	ML(gravelly silt)
SL3	26.04	50.68	23.29	ML(sand silt with gravelly)
SL4	45.18	35.99	18.83	ML(gravelly silt with sand)
AV	46.81	35.655	17.535	

Table 3: Sieve analysis result Summary and Classification

Figure 1: Sieve graphs all sample analyzed

3.4 Moisture content

Moisture content done according to the procedure described in BS 1377- 2:1990 (BSI, 1990), mass of water to the mass of dry sample estimated in percentage helps in physical classification of soil, result summarized in table 4.

Sites	Depth (m),	Moisture (%)
SL1	2	13.49
SL2	2	19.00
SL3	2	11.38
SL4	2	17.39
Average		15.31

Table 4: Summary of moisture content results

3.5 Optimum moisture content and dry density (proctor test)

The compaction tests results are shown by the figure 2 and summarized in table 5 determine the maximum compaction and water required to get them, the procedure section in BS 1377- 4:1990 (BSI, 1990).

Sites	Depth (m)	Dry density Mg/m ³	Moisture content (%)
SL1	2	1.981	8.72
SL2	2	1.985	10.5
SL3	2	2.02	9.26
SL4	2	2.019	9.25
Average		2	9.43

Table 5: Summary of Compaction test results

Figure 2: Proctor graph of all sites

3.6 Atterberg limits plastic/liquid limits

The procedure to analyze limits in sites is described in BS 1377- 2:1990 (BSI, 1990) and the plastic determined by rolling the sample which is in plastics range and liquid limit is determined by using Cassagrande method.

Sites	Depth (m),	Liquid limits	Plastic limits	Plastics index
SL1	2	33.5	24.4	9
SL2	2	28.1	18.2	10
SL3	2	33.2	27.1	6
SL4	2	23.3	15	8

Table 6: Summary of Atterberg limits test results.

3.7 Shear test Result

Shear test is test done on subsoil in order to design sliding like retaining wall and other retaining structures as it described in procedure BS 1377- 7:1990. And give us two parameter cohesion (ϕ) and friction (\bar{C}), (BSI, 1990). Results of each site are shown by the figure 3 and the lateritic soil parameters of shear are summarized in table 7.

Sites	Cohesion (ϕ)	Friction (\bar{C})
SL1	39.1	58.1
SL2	23.1	55.9
SL3	17.1	51.7
SL4	46.7	57.2

Table 7: Strength parameters of undisturbed soil (shear test)

SHEAR CHART

Figure 3: Mohr- Coulomb failure envelope, all sites

3.8 CBR Test Analysis

The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) is a semi empirical test that is often employed in the estimation of the bearing capacity of sub-grade, sub-base and base materials (Simon, 1973). The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test was conducted on lateritic soils from NYARUGURU, according to procedures specified in BS 1377- 4, Clause 7:1990 (BSI, 1990). Results of each site are shown by the figure 4.

Figure 4: CBR curve of laterites from Nyaruguru District

3.9 Consolidation Result Analysis

Consolidation test is used to determine the rate and magnitude of settlement in soil the settlement in soil values obtained by this test are due to primary consolidation only which is 90% of the total consolidation (t_{90}), the results are helpful to design foundation (DAS, 2010). The results have been compiled in Table 8 below.

Sites	Coefficient of compressibility(a_v)	Compression index(C_c)	Coefficient Of Consolidation(C_v)
SL1	0.00067	0.078	35
SL2	0.00048	0.082	4.3
SL3	0.00016	0.084	4.0
SL4	0.00037	0.095	1.0

Table 8: Consolidation data all sites

4. Discussions

4.1 Specific gravity discussions

The specific gravity of the soil depends on the amount of sand and also depends on their mineral constituents and mode of formation of the soil. According to the table 2 the specific gravity for the studied soil samples ranged from 2.66 to 2.93. According to specification, a good lateritic material should have specific gravity ranging from 2.6-2.80 (Sujeeth, 2015). Based on this fact, samples from the study area is considered to be acceptably high which is indicate that our soil is good which is sand and gravel with low silt and clay, the site of SL1 and SL4 have high specific gravity have also reddish color those are the best comparing to the others, by comparing to the other laterites in table 9. The specific gravity of the soil depends on the amount of sand and also depends on their mineral constituents and mode of formation of the soil.

Reference Sites	Test Condition	Specific Gravity range (Gs)	Average Specific Gravity range(Gs)
NYARUGURU	Air dried	2.66 to 2.93	2.77
Nilai sites A,B,C,D,E (Sujeeth, 2015)	Air dried	2.66 to 3.02	2.78
Welega, Ethiopia (Zelalem, 2005)	Air dried	2.78 to 3.03	2.90
Niger Delta, Nigeria (Ugbe, 2011)	Air dried	2.50 to 2.83	2.62

Table 9: Specific gravity of sample from reference site

4.2 Particle size Distribution analysis discussions

The particle size distribution of all site of laterites from NYARUGURU was found as it shown in figure 1 and table 3, all sample have high quantity of coarse gravelly soil the average is 46.81% all are above 45.18% except sample SL3 which have 26.04%, by using USC classification shown that all site it is gravelly silt unless SL1 which is CL (sand lean clay with gravel), as described by the AASTHO Classification of soil and their use on road layers, SL1, SL2 and SL3 are categorized as A-2-4 silty and clayey gravel and sand which are excellent to be used as sub-grade and SL4 is A-1-b which is Stone fragment gravel and sand also excellent on sub-grade layer tested according to ASTM C136 on sub-grade use the percentage passing on sieve of 0.075 mm

must be 0-15%, hence SL1 and SL2 meet the requirement to be used as sub-base layer (Das, 2002).

4.3 Moisture content discussions

The moisture content describes the soil physically it ranges between 11.38 to 19% as per table 4, with an average value of 15.21%. Most natural soils, which are sandy and gravelly in nature, may have water contents up to about 15 to 20% (Das, 2002). In natural fine-grained (silty or clayey) soils, water contents up to about 50 to 80% can be found. However, peat and highly organic soils with water contents up to about 500% are not uncommon, means our laterites are sandy gravelly in nature. Federal Ministry of Works and Housing (1972) for road works recommend liquid limits of 50% maximum for sub-base and base materials. The results of the soil samples fall within allowed specification, thus making them suitable for sub-base and base materials.

4.4 Optimum moisture content and dry density discussions (proctor test)

The compaction parameters in the table 5 show that OPM are below 10 % and dry density ranged between 1.981 to 2.02 modified proctor methods which good to be used in sub-grade and sub-base, compaction densify the soils, increasing dry unit weight with the addition of water. This decreases the settlement effect, decreases permeability and also increases shear strength, the highest limitation when water helps in maximizing the dry density is the maximum dry density beyond which the soil loses its density. The results are comparable to the results of other study where the optimum water content, OWC and maximum dry unit weight, γ_d , max values range from 11% to 23% and 15 to 20 kN/m³ for the fine-grained soils, from 7% to 12% and 19.5 to 21.5kN/m³ for the lateritic soil sand and from 6% to 7% and 22.2 to 22.8kN/m³ for the crushed rocks (Horpibulsun, 2012).

4.5 Atterberg limits plastic/liquid limits discussions

According to the table 6 the range of results of liquid limits vary from 33.2 to 48%, plastic limits from 24.4 to 31.3% and plastic index varied from 6 to 17%. In another study done by Layade, the liquid limits ranged from 12.0% to 40.1%, the plastic limits varied from 10.0% and 22.0% while the plastic index is 2.8 to 20.4 (Layade Gideon Oluyinka 1*, 2018). Federal Ministry of Work and Housing recommends liquid limits of 50% maximum for sub-base and base materials

for road works (Federal Ministry of work and Housing, 1997). All the studied soil samples fall within these specifications which make them suitable for sub-base and base materials.

4.6 California Bearing Ratio (CBR) discussions

The CBR is a semi empirical test that is often employed in the estimation of the bearing capacity of sub-grade, sub-base and base materials. The unsoaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR) values for the lateritic soil samples range from 14.17% to 32.90%. Federal Ministry of Works and Housing recommendation for soils use as sub-grade, sub-base and base materials are: $\leq 10\%$, $\leq 30\%$ and $\leq 80\%$ respectively for unsoaked soil (Federal Ministry of work and Housing, 1997). This implies that locations SL2, SL3 and SL4 with values less than 30% are excellent sub-base materials, SL1 having values less than 80% is good for base materials.

5. Conclusion

Lateritic soils found in Nyaruguru District and their geotechnical engineering properties have been investigated and according to the obtained results, visually the soils are of gravel content with reddish or light brownish colour.

According to the study findings, fines were found to be of 17.5%, Sands were 35.6% and Gravels of 46.81%. Classification of soils using USCS revealed that overall the lateritic soils are classified as gravelly silt. Natural moisture content ranged between 18 to 24% at a mean value of 26% while compaction test revealed a maximum dry unit weight (MDD) of 20.01 KN/m³ and optimum moisture content (OMC) of 9.43 % respectively. Gs was found to be between 2.66 and 2.93 with an average of 2.77. Plastic limits range between 15 to 27.1%, liquid limits 22.3 to 33.5% and plasticity index 6 to 10 %. This suggests that the soils could be described as having a low to medium swell. Shear strength parameters c and ϕ were found to be 31.5 KN and 55.7° respectively which suggest moderate bearing capacity with applications of slope stability. CBR was found to range between 14.17 to 32.9%. Road sub-grade applications are also a viable choice given the CBR results, although stabilization of soil is required in such an application to increase durability.

The discussion of results shows that lateritic soil present throughout the study area SL1, SL2, SL3 and SL4 are suitable for sub-grade while SL1 and SL2 are also suitable for sub-base material since their geotechnical properties fall within the regulatory standards.

References

- [1] Addson, G. K. (June 2008). *Availability of Natural Gravel for Road construction in Ghana*. KUMASI: Kwame Nkrumah University.
- [2] Ademila, O. (August 2017). Geosciences Research, Vol. 2, No. 3, August 2017. *Engineering Evaluation of Lateritic Soils of Failed Highway Sections in Southwestern Nigeria* , 9.
- [3] Amadi A.N.*, A. W. (January 03, 2015). Assessment of the Geotechnical Properties of Lateritic Soils in Minna, North Central Nigeria for Road design and Construction. *American Journal of Mining and Metallurgy*, 2015, Vol. 3, No. 1, 15-20 , 1.
- [4] ASTM International, A. D. (2018). *Standard Test Methods for Specific Gravity of Soil Solids by Water Pycnometer (ASTM D854)*. USA: ASTM International.
- [5] Bell, F. G. (2007). *Engineering Geology*. Oxford OX2 8DP, UK: Oxford.
- [6] BS:1377:4, S. B. (1990). Part 4: Compaction-related tests. In B. STANDARD, *Methods of test for Soils for civil engineering purposes* (p. 70). BRITISH STANDARD.
- [7] BSI. (1990). *Methods of test for Soils for civil engineering purposes*. London,UK: British Standard International.
- [8] Creswell, J. (2002). Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and. *Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill Prentice Hall*.
- [8] DAS, B. M. (2010). *Principles of Geotechnical Engineering*. United States of America: BRAJA M. DAS.
- [9] Das, B. M. (2002). *SOIL MECHANICS*. New York: OXFORD UNIVERSITY PRESS.
- [10] Federal Ministry of work and Housing. (1997). *General Specification for aroads and Bridges, Volume II*. Lagos, Nigeria: Federal Highway Department.
- [11] Gidigasu, M. (1976). *Laterite soil engineering*. Amsterdam: Elsevier Scientific Pub.co.
- [12] Horpibulsun, S. (2012). *Compaction behavior of fine-grained Soil, Lateritic Soils and Crushed rocks*. Thailand: Construction and infrastructure Management and School of Civil Engineering , Suranaree University of Technology.
- [13] Intercontinental Consultants and Technocrats Pvt, t. (February, 2017). *RESETTLEMENT ACTION PLAN FOR INDICATIVE FEEDER ROADS*. NYARUGURU DISTRICT: MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND ANIMAL RESOURCES.
- [14] Jamal, H. (2017, mars 23). *Typical Road Structure Details*. Retrieved from Civil Engineering | Civil Engg Lectures, Books, Notes, Softwares site: <https://www.aboutcivil.org/road-structure-cross-section.html>
- [15] K.H.Head, M. E. (1992). *Manual of Soil Laboratory Testing*. Scotland, UK: Whittless Publishing.
- [16] Layade Gideon Oluyinka 1*, O. C. (2018). Geotechnical properties of lateritic soil as subgrade and base. *International Journal of Advanced Geosciences*, 6 (1) (2018) 78-82 , 6.
- [17] Md.FazluHaque, E. (2001). *Construction Practices and Procedures Manual*. SarakBhaban ,Ramna, Dhaka.

- [18] Nikolaides, A. (2015). *Pavements, Materials and Control of Quality*. Boca Raton London New York: Taylor & Francis Group, LLC.
- [19] NYARUGURU. (2018). *DISTRICT DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY*. NYARUGURU: NYARUGURU DISTRICT.
- [20] Oladele A. Omotoso1, O. J. (June 5, 2012). Engineering Properties of Lateritic Soils around Dall Quarry in Sango. *Earth Science Research; Vol. 1, No. 2; 2012* , 3.
- [21] Omotoso1, O. J. (June 5, 2012). Engineering Properties of Lateritic Soils around Dall Quarry in Sango. *Earth Science Research; Vol. 1, No. 2; 2012* , 3
- [22] Patrick N. Lemougna, U. F. (2011). *Laterite Based Stabilized Products for Sustainable Building Applications in Tropical Countries: Review and Prospects for the Case of Cameroon*. Cameroon.
- [23] Sehgal, J. (1998). *RED & LATERITIC SOILS*. New Delhi: INDIAN SOCIETY OF SOIL SURVEY ANQ LAND USE PLANNING.
- [24] Simon, A. G. (1973). Use of lateritic soil for road construction in North Dahomey, Engineerin Geology, 7:197-218. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-7952\(73\)90031-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-7952(73)90031-8).
- [25] STANDARD, B. (1990). BS 1377 Part 2: Classification tests. In B. STANDARD, *Methods of test for Soils for civil engineering purposes* (p. 73). BRITISH STANDARD.
- [26] Standard, B. (1990). BS 1377-7:1990 ,Part 7: Shear strength tests (total stress). In B. Standard, *Methods of test for Soils for civil engineering purposes* (p. 57). Standard, British.
- [27] Sujeeth, A. (APRIL 2015). *AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING PROPERTIES OF LATERITE SOILS IN NILAI, MALAYSIA* , 89.
- [28] Syed Muhammad Sajjad Kabir. (2016). District Development Strategy (2018/19-2023/24), https://nyaruguru.gov.rw/fileadmin/templates/document/Website/Final_DDS_for_Nyaruguru_District.pdf . *Elementary Education Online* .
- [29] Testing, A. S. Aggregate or Granular Subbase Section 02230. In A. S. Materials, *Tender document Specifications Division 2 Site works*. U.K: American Society for Testing and Materials.
- [30] TY-JOUR, W. W.-E. (2017). *Assessment of Laterite Suuitable for Road Construction In Bafang Area (West-Cameroon) Based on Physical Properties, Geo-Environmental Factors And GIS Software VL-Vol.4JO*. Bafang: Journal of Multidiplinary Engineering Science and Technology(JMEST).
- [31] Ugbe, F. (2011). Research Journal of Environmental and Earth Sciences 3(5): 571-577, 2011. *Basic Engineering Geological Properties of Lateritic Soils from Western Niger Delta* , 1.
- [32] Zelalem, A. (2005). *Basic Engineering Properties of Lateritic Soils*. Addis Ababa.: Addis Ababa University.

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All praises and thanks be to God Almighty.

Dedication

I dedicate this study to our families.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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